

Enantioselective Hydrogenation of Ketones by Iridium Nanoparticles Ligated with Chiral Secondary Phosphine Oxides†

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ABSTRACT: Chiral iridium nanoparticles (**IrNPs**) were synthesized by H₂ reduction of (1,5-cyclooctadiene)(methoxy)iridium(I) dimer ([Ir(OMe)(COD)]₂) in the presence of an asymmetric secondary phosphine oxide (4,5-dihydro-3*H*-dinaphtho[2,1-*c*:1',2'-*e*]phosphepine-4-oxide, **L**). This highly reproducible and simple procedure furnished small, well dispersed and soluble nanoparticles of 1.4 (0.2) nm, which were found to be active catalysts for the enantioselective hydrogenation of prochiral ketones. This study represents the first example of asymmetric hydrogenation catalyzed by SPO-ligated metal nanoparticles and also the first example of asymmetric hydrogenation catalyzed by *non*-supported chiral IrNPs. The IrNPs were characterized by the use of a wide variety of techniques, such as TEM, HRTEM, EDX, XPS, ATR FT-IR, ECD, and MAS-NMR spectroscopy with and without ¹H-¹³C cross-polarization (CP).

INTRODUCTION

During the last decade, secondary phosphine oxide (SPO) ligands have been revealed as an attractive alternative to classic tertiary phosphorus ligands in catalysis,¹ as SPOs are usually more stable towards air and moisture than their phosphine and phosphite counterparts.² Their strong donor properties,³ higher stability, and straightforward preparation make SPOs ideal ligands for homogeneous metal catalysis.^{1,3a} Free SPO

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exists as an equilibrium between the pentavalent phosphine oxide, $RR'P^{(+V)}(H)O$, and the trivalent phosphinous acid, $RR'P^{(+III)}(OH)$. This equilibrium generally lies towards the air-stable pentavalent oxide form, but upon coordination via the phosphorus atom to a suitable transition metal it is displaced in favour of the phosphinous (P^{+III}) tautomer (Scheme 1a).⁴ The resulting complexes (Scheme 1a) have shown a special ability to cleave H_2 heterolytically through the metal M and the oxygen atom O (Scheme 1b).^{1a-d,m} DFT calculations showed that in Rh hydrogen transfer reactions, a direct outer sphere transfer of hydrogen to ketones is the most plausible pathway (Scheme 1c). This ligand-metal cooperative effect has been widely used in catalysis, including asymmetric hydrogenation, in which such reactivity is particularly notorious.^{3a,5}

Scheme 1 (a) Tautomeric forms of SPOs and formation of metal complexes; (b) Heterolytic cleavage of H_2 ; (c) Transition state for the transfer of hydrogen to ketones catalyzed by Rh-SPO complexes.

Our group applied this concept for hydrogenation reactions, developed for homogeneous catalysts, also on metal nanoparticles (MNPs) stabilized by SPOs.⁶⁻⁷ We proposed that SPO ligands coordinate strongly to MNPs acting as heterolytic activators for H_2 cooperatively with a neighbouring metal atom. Indeed, spectroscopic studies showed that aromatic SPOs coordinate to gold nanoparticles in their anionic form $Au-P(O)R_2$; these AuNPs are very selective catalysts for the hydrogenation of substituted aldehydes.⁷

For asymmetric hydrogenation using ligand modified MNPs, only a few ligands have been reported in the literature,⁸ most of them concerning cinchonidine⁹ and proline¹⁰ systems. Moreover, except one example of Liu *et al.*,¹¹ the use of iridium nanoparticles (IrNPs) in enantioselective hydrogenation is limited to heterogeneous systems mainly based on preformed nanoparticles modified by the addition of e.g. cinchona alkaloids and their derivatives, chiral diamines, and diphosphines.¹² The latter two systems

employ the same ligands as known for homogeneous systems, which raises some doubts about their heterogeneous character, but definite proof for either mode of action is difficult to obtain.¹³ The use of SPO ligands stabilizing MNPs is still in its infancy and, to the best of our knowledge, chiral SPOs have not yet been employed as ligands of MNPs for their use in asymmetric catalysis.^{8f,14}

It has been suggested that the fluxionality of the ligand at the metal surface can reduce or annul chiral induction.¹⁵ Thus, we hypothesized that strongly coordinating ligands, apart from being powerful stabilizing agents, should create a rigid, asymmetric environment and favour the induction of enantioselectivity in asymmetric transformations catalyzed by MNPs.

In the present work we report the first example of enantioselective hydrogenation catalyzed by *non*-supported chiral IrNPs.¹⁶ To this end, we have successfully prepared chiral IrNPs with an asymmetric secondary phosphine oxide, 4,5-dihydro-3*H*-dinaphtho[2,1-*c*:1',2'-*e*] phosphepine-4-oxide (**L**, Fig. 1) introduced by Gulyás *et al.*¹⁷ This SPO ligand was chosen because it does not racemize,^{1*m*} while other chiral SPOs were thought to racemize easily when used in homogeneous catalysis.^{5*a-b*} The so-obtained IrNPs showed moderate enantioselectivities in the asymmetric hydrogenation of prochiral ketones without the need of any other additives. In addition, the metal surface of these IrNPs was studied through the coordination of CO by magic angle spinning solid state NMR (MAS-NMR) and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) techniques.

Fig. 1 Chiral secondary phosphine oxide (**L**) employed in this study (*S* enantiomer is depicted).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IrNPs are generally prepared by reduction of Ir(I) or Ir(III) precursors with an appropriate reducing agent such as H₂, NaBH₄, etc.¹⁶ The addition of a ligand as stabilizing agent provides an electronic/steric protection, controlling the process of growth of the MNPs and avoiding aggregation. Inspired by a procedure previously described for RuNPs,^{6,18} the iridium nanoparticles (**IrNPs**) were prepared at room temperature (R.T.) by H₂ reduction of (1,5-cyclooctadiene)(methoxy)iridium(I) dimer

$[\text{Ir}(\text{OMe})(\text{COD})]_2$ in tetrahydrofuran (THF) and in the presence of 0.5 eq (based on Ir) of enantiopure **L** (Scheme 2, for further details see ESI†).

Scheme 2 Synthesis of **IrNPs** from $[\text{Ir}(\text{OMe})(\text{COD})]_2$ and **L**.

The metallic precursor ($[\text{Ir}(\text{OMe})(\text{COD})]_2$) generates only volatile by-products during the MNP synthesis under hydrogen, such as methanol and cyclooctane. As a consequence, the **IrNPs** were formed cleanly without impurities or residual salts, and their surface was only covered by chiral ligands added for their stabilization and hydrides stemming from H_2 (*vide infra*). The IrNPs obtained were highly soluble in THF but slightly soluble in methanol (MeOH), thus simplifying the purification step by repeated precipitation in MeOH. The purified nanoparticles were fully characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), high resolution TEM (HRTEM), elemental analysis (EA), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), attenuated total reflection (ATR) FT-IR, MAS-NMR, and UV-vis circular dichroism (ECD). TEM images revealed the presence of small and well-dispersed nanoparticles with a size *ca.* 1.4 (0.2) nm (Fig. 2, for more details see ESI†). As a first result, the SPO ligand **L** was found to be an efficient ligand for the formation of iridium nanoparticles with a narrow size distribution.

Fig. 2 Representative TEM image of **IrNPs** and diameter distribution determined from TEM images by counting > 300 non-touching particles obtained from images captured from distinct quadrants of the grid.

As shown in Figure 3, HRTEM studies revealed highly crystalline **IrNPs** with a cubic close-packed structure (ccp) for which fast fourier transformation (FFT) displayed reflections to the (111), (200) and (111) atomic planes (Fig. 3b and 3c).

Fig. 3 (a) HRTEM of IrNPs; (b) HRTEM of a single IrNP; (c) Fast Fourier Transform of a single particle shown in panel b).

Elemental analysis of the **IrNPs** gave an Ir content of 49.1%, which is in good agreement with the value measured by EDX (47.3%, Fig. S2†). The amounts of carbon and phosphorus observed by EA (38.8 and 4.5%, respectively) were in good accord with the ratio of these elements in **L** (80.5 and 9.4%, respectively), suggesting that the ligand remained intact at the iridium surface. EA was consistent with a metal–ligand ratio of 1.75:1 (Table 1). It is worth noting that the Ir/L ratio accounts for a large amount of SPO coordinated to the NP surface, since the approximate number of ligands is only slightly lower than the number of surface atoms.

Table 1 Analytical data of the **IrNPs**.

Diameter (nm)	Ir Content (%)	Ir : L Ratio
1.45 ± 0.16	49.1	1.75 : 1

The coordination of **L** to the nanoparticle surface was demonstrated by solid state MAS NMR. The $^{31}\text{P}\{^1\text{H}\}$ MAS NMR spectrum of **IrNPs** exhibits an unique signal at 94 ppm (Fig. S19†) which corresponds to the chemical shift of coordinated ligand **L** (the signal of free **L** is located at 46 ppm). The $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ MAS NMR spectrum (Fig. S18†) presents

two peaks at ca. 131 and 126 ppm that correspond to the aromatic rings and a group of signals centered at ca. 29 ppm that can be attributed to the methylene groups and to the cyclohexyl groups obtained by a partial hydrogenation of ligand during the synthesis under H₂. The peak at ca. 66 ppm is most likely due to MeOH.

The surface of MNPs, which are prepared by hydrogenation of a metallic precursor in presence of a stabilizer, is often covered by hydrides.¹⁹ Following a procedure previously reported for RuNPs, we quantified the surface hydrides through the reduction of 2-norbornene by reaction with the **IrNPs**.²⁰ The amount of norbornane formed was monitored by gas chromatography (GC), showing that these **IrNPs** display 1.3 H per surface Ir atom (section 7, ESI†), which supports the higher value observed for H in the EA. The small excess of oxygen observed by EA can be explained by a partial oxidation of iridium, probably due to the presence of traces of oxygen during sample preparation. The Ir 4f XPS spectrum of **IrNPs** exhibits binding energies of 61.3 and 64.2 eV for Ir 4f_{7/2} and Ir 4f_{5/2}, respectively (Fig. S1†), showing higher energy values than the ones found in the literature for Ir(0) (60.6–61.0 and 63.2–63.6 eV are regarded as metallic Ir),^{12a,d,21} but lower than the values of iridium dioxide, IrO₂ (61.6–62.3 and 64.4–65.7 eV).^{21b,c,22} These values indicate the presence of Ir(I) atoms,²³ as a result of the binding with SPO molecules, and the formation of some IrO₂ on the NP surface. The fitting of the XPS spectrum resulted in six contributions (Fig. 4) with binding energies of 60.6, 61.2, 62.2, 63.3, 64.3 and 65.5 eV, of which 60.6 and 63.3 correspond to metallic iridium, 61.2 and 64.3 to Ir(I), and 62.2 and 65.5 to IrO₂.

Fig. 4 XPS spectrum with fitting of Ir 4f signals for **IrNPs**.

The ATR FT-IR spectrum of the free SPO ligand shows the P–H stretching absorption at 2327 cm^{-1} (Fig. S7†). Such a P–H band is clearly absent in the ATR FT-IR spectrum of the **IrNPs** (Fig. S8-S9†). In the 3500 cm^{-1} region only a very small absorption is seen, indicating that the concentration of species containing POH must be small. The absence of protons suggests a similar binding mode of **L** on the **IrNPs** surface to that previously described for gold nanoparticles, *i.e.* a purely anionic SPO ligand is present.⁷ This means that hydrogenation and hydrogen transfer can take place the same way as previously proposed for AuNPs and several homogeneous complexes of Pt and Rh. Furthermore, the characteristic broad band at *ca.* 550 cm^{-1} related to the Ir–O vibration was not detected,²⁴ which points to sample manipulation being responsible for the presence of IrO₂ in the XPS spectrum. Finally, an intense band at *ca.* 1984 cm^{-1} was observed in the spectrum of **IrNPs**. This band was identified as CO coordinated on the nanoparticle surface, which probably arises from a decarbonylation process of THF and/or methoxide during the synthesis, as previously observed for RuNPs.²⁵ The intensity of this band increased after the exposition of the **IrNPs** to a CO atmosphere (1 bar, R. T., 24 hours, Fig. S10†), confirming the presence of CO coordinated at the Ir surface in the purified nanoparticles.

Taking benefit of the coordination of CO to the **IrNPs**, ^{13}C O was used as a probe molecule in order to study the location of the open sites at their surface by solid state MAS-NMR with and without ^1H - ^{13}C cross-polarization (CP). Thus, the **IrNPs** were exposed to 1 bar of ^{13}C O at R.T. for 20 h. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ MAS spectrum displays two signals at ca. 165 and 190 ppm which correspond to CO coordinated on the NP surface (Fig. 5A and Fig. S22†).²⁶ The broad band at ca. 190 ppm is assigned to CO coordinated in a bridging mode (CO_b), while the sharp signal around 165 ppm belongs to CO coordinated in a terminal mode (CO_t). Previous studies about CO coordination on RuNPs have demonstrated that CO_b molecules coordinate onto faces and CO_t onto edges and apexes.^{20b,25} The low intensity of the peak for CO_b indicates that the number of available faces on the **IrNPs** is low, which is in good agreement with their small size and the high coverage by SPO ligands and hydrides. On the other hand, the high intensity of the peak at 165 ppm points to a large quantity of CO_t and thus to a high number of surface sites available for their coordination. In addition, these CO_t molecules are static on the Ir surface as revealed by the presence of spinning side bands (*).

In the $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ CP-MAS spectrum (Fig. 5B and Fig. S23†) the intensity of the signal for both CO_b and CO_t decreased by the same ratio, which evidences that the two types of CO are affected by CP in the same way. This is in contrast to earlier findings for RuNPs for which it was concluded that CO_b are not located in the proximity of the phosphine ligands, while CO_t are close to phosphine ligands.^{20b,27} The high loading of SPO ligands explains that ^{13}C nuclei in both sites experience the vicinity of H atoms in these IrNPs. The presence of bulky ligands, such as **L**, in the vicinity of CO molecules could limit their mobility to some extent. Indeed, the presence of spinning side bands suggests that CO_t are static on the Ir surface. More precisely, in the $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ CP-MAS spectrum the intensity of these spinning side bands decreased around 50% less in comparison with the main signal. This indicates that approximately 50% of the total CO_t molecules are static on the surface.

Fig. 5 $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ MAS NMR (A) and $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ CP-MAS NMR (B) spectra of **IrNPs** after exposure to ^{13}CO (1 bar; R. T.; 20 h). Asterisks denote spinning side bands.

The chirality of the **IrNPs** was examined by circular dichroism (ECD) spectroscopy (Fig. 6B). Interestingly the nanoparticles, stabilized with the *R* and *S* enantiomer respectively, exhibited a clear mirror-image signal in their ECD spectra, while the

typical bisignate character of the binaphthyl ligand (Fig. 6A) has disappeared. Coordination of one of the naphthyl rings to the Ir surface might affect the ECD spectrum and distort the bisignate appearance but for steric reasons this coordination seems very unlikely. Besides, the effect of this distortion does not spoil the bisignate character completely as shown for calculations on coordination of helicenes to a gold surface in an isotropic medium.²⁸ The absorptions and Cotton effects above 350 nm show that IrNP absorptions are a component of the ECD spectrum. In these small nanoclusters the spectroscopic properties can be described as for molecular species as they do not show surface plasmon resonance. Thus we conclude that the ECD spectrum is the sum of contributions, namely a NP part and a bisignate ligand spectrum. The IrNPs are a mixture of different sizes and distinct bands due to individual d-d transitions that lead to a multisignate ECD spectrum cannot be observed.²⁹ Instead, both the UV-vis spectrum (Fig. S6†) and the ECD spectrum of IrNPs show a continuous decrease from 250 to 500 nm and summing up this spectrum with the slightly distorted, but still bisignate, binaphthyl part gives the resulting spectra in Fig. 5B. It should be noted that the IrNPs are not necessarily intrinsically chiral as are several reported Au thiolate clusters, e.g. enantio-separated Au₃₈ ligated with 24 thiolates.³⁰ The Cotton effect in the d-d transitions of the IrNPs is due to induced ECD,³¹ as is generally assumed;³² an orbital interaction between the metal core and the ligands may lead to Cotton effects in the spectrum of the metal nanocluster, in the same way as has been known for years in d-d and f-f transitions in chiral metal complexes of Co, Ru, and rare earth metals.³³

Fig. 6 (A) ECD spectra of ligand *R* (L_R) and *S* (L_S). (B) ECD spectra of IrNPs, enantiomers **R** and **S**.

The chirality of the NPs induced by the asymmetric ligands (observed by CD) and the proximity of these to free active sites (as evidenced by MAS-NMR through the

coordination of CO) prompted us to evaluate the catalytic performance of these new **IrNPs** in asymmetric hydrogenation. Thus, the **IrNPs** were used in the enantioselective hydrogenation of acetophenone (Scheme 3). Indeed, the **IrNPs** were found to be enantioselective catalysts for the hydrogenation of ketones and the corresponding alcohol was obtained with 30% conversion and 25% ee at R.T. and MeOH as solvent.

Scheme 3 Asymmetric hydrogenation of acetophenone catalyzed by **IrNPs**.

Given this first interesting result, the reaction conditions were optimized in order to improve the enantioselectivity. The screening of different solvents revealed a non-negligible influence of the medium, THF being the most favourable solvent to perform the experiments (from 25% ee in MeOH to 55% ee in THF). Room temperature was the best choice since worse results were observed at other temperatures. Under the optimal reaction conditions (for further details see ESI[†]), the chiral product was obtained with 88% conversion and 55% ee (Table 2, entry 1). Next, the potential of the **IrNPs** was evaluated in the asymmetric hydrogenation of several substituted aromatic ketones and ethyl pyruvate (Table 2). An array of substituted alcohols was generated in moderate to good conversions with promising enantioselectivities for these new systems. In very few cases, hydrogenation of the aromatic ring as minor by-product was observed (<5%). This is not surprising as due to the crowded surface and the small size of the **IrNPs**, the available faces (necessary to hydrogenate phenyl groups) are scarce.

Table 2 Enantioselective hydrogenation of prochiral ketones catalyzed by **IrNPs**.^a

Entry	Substrate	IrNP	Conversion (%) ^b	ee (%) ^b	Configuration
1		R	88	55	S
2		S	47	52	R
3		R	38	30	S
4		S	11	27	R
5		R	90 13	22	S

6		S	38	20	R
7		R	63	56	S
8		S	14	39	R
9		R	100	10	S
10		S	100	8	R
11		R	98	50	S
12		S	51	34	R
13		R	100	26	S
14		S	100	30	R

^a Reagents and conditions: IrNPs (0.0025 mmol of Ir assuming % of Ir from elemental analysis), substrate (0.25 mmol), THF (0.75 mL), 18 h, R.T., 40 bar H₂. ^b Conversions and %ee were determined by GC (average of two runs).

While the CD spectra of the enantiomeric **IrNPs** are exact mirror images, the catalytic results are not and we assume that some deterioration of the IrNPs had occurred. The presence of substituents with steric influence in α -position did not improve the enantioselectivity (entries 3–6), whereas the introduction of an electron-withdrawing group such as CF₃ in the same place activated the ketone function, which led to an increase of the conversion but also a diminution of the enantioselectivity (entries 9–10). On the other hand, an electron-withdrawing group in p -position of the aromatic ring raised the activity more than an electron donor substituent, while both experiments gave a similar enantioselectivity (entries 7–8 and 11–12). Finally, the asymmetric hydrogenation of an aliphatic ketone (ethyl pyruvate) resulted in a complete conversion and moderate enantioselectivity (entries 13–14).

There are several works reporting the asymmetric hydrogenation of ketones catalyzed by iridium nanoparticles. However, nearly all of these studies referred to heterogeneous systems, while the majority of them achieved the asymmetric induction by the addition of a modifier to preformed achiral nanoparticles.¹² In addition, many of these systems required the presence of a base,^{12a-d,f-g} such as *t*BuOK, LiOH or NaOH as is typical of homogeneous systems.³⁴ It is worth noting that the well-defined and *non*-supported chiral IrNPs described herein did not require any base or additive.

As Ir(I)–SPO systems have been employed as catalyst in homogeneous enantioselective hydrogenation,^{5a-b} a set of control experiments were performed in order to clarify whether the enantioselectivity was induced by the **IrNPs** or by a homogeneous catalyst formed *in situ* (Table 3). First, no ³¹P signals of Ir-SPO complexes could be observed in the solution ³¹P{¹H} NMR spectrum of the purified nanoparticles. The use of a mixture of iridium precursor ([CODIr(MeO)]₂) and SPO ligand displayed much lower activity and enantioselectivity than the **IrNPs** in the asymmetric hydrogenation of acetophenone (Table 3, entries 1 and 4). Such a mixture showed a similar behaviour after 1 and 2 days of incubation (entries 5 and 6), and even the presence of nanoparticles was observed once finished the catalytic experiment (Fig. S15-S16†) and these could be responsible for the activity. Additionally, unwashed NPs, which could contain a homogeneous catalyst, provided worse results than purified NPs (entry 3). The use of ethyl pyruvate as substrate led to similar observations (section 5, ESI†). Next, a mercury poisoning test was carried out, since mercury can selectively poison MNPs by amalgamation, which allows discerning between homogeneous or nanoparticle catalysis, although exceptions have been noted and definite proof is not easily obtained.^{13,35} The poisoning experiment led to the complete inhibition of the reaction (entry 2), confirming that the NPs were responsible for the catalysis. All together, these results emphasize the role of the **IrNPs** as catalyst to perform the asymmetric hydrogenation of ketones and they disprove a major role for homogeneous catalysts.

Table 3 Summary of the attempted enantioselective hydrogenation of acetophenone using various iridium catalytic systems.^a

Entry	Catalyst	Conversion (%) ^b	ee (%) ^b	Configuration
1 ^c	IrNP	88	55	S
2 ^d	IrNP + Hg	1	--	--
3 ^c	IrNP (unwashed)	21	28	S
4 ^e	[(COD)Ir(MeO)] ₂ + L ^f	6	26	S
5 ^{e,g}	[(COD)Ir(MeO)] ₂ + L ^f	3	32	S

6 ^{e,h}	[(COD)Ir(MeO)] ₂ + L ^f	3	30	S
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^a Conditions: 18 h, R. T. ^b Conversions and %ee were determined by GC (average of two runs). ^c IrNPs (0.0025 mmol of Ir assuming % of Ir from elemental analysis), substrate (0.25 mmol), THF (0.75 mL). ^d 400 eq Hg were added. ^e [(COD)Ir(MeO)]₂ (0.005 mmol), L (0.02 mmol), substrate (1 mmol), THF (3 mL). ^f The presence of nanoparticles was observed once finished the catalytic experiment. ^g 24 h incubation. ^h 48 incubation.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have successfully used an asymmetric secondary phosphine oxide for the synthesis of well-defined chiral iridium nanoparticles, in which the chirality of the IrNPs is induced by the ligand. The optically active nanoparticles, ligated by the *R* and *S* enantiomers, showed excellent mirror-image ECD spectra. Moreover, these types of IrNPs are active catalysts for the asymmetric hydrogenation of ketones, which makes it the first example of enantioselective hydrogenation catalyzed by *non*-supported chiral IrNPs. Furthermore, an extensive characterization of the IrNPs was performed by several procedures. Specifically, MAS-NMR experiments allowed us to study the surface chemistry and the location of the active sites. The studies evidence that ¹³CO coordinates mainly in a terminal mode. The proximity of the rigidly bound asymmetric ligands to free active sites enables the enantioselective formation of products, for instance by aligning the substrate via a hydrogen bond thus inducing enantioselectivity. Although the ees are as yet modest, a new chiral ligand type has been added to the toolbox of asymmetric catalysis with MNPs. In this first study only one ligand, selected for its inability to racemize, was used, but after this thorough analysis the road seems open for many related ligands and polar substrates.

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